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The Pains and Gains of Being a Social Studies Teacher

Teaching Social Studies goes beyond delivering facts about history, geography, government, and culture. It is a commitment to develop learned and informed citizens. A Social Studies teacher goes through pains and gains in the profession. While it can be challenging, its rewards make up for all challenges. One of the most rewarding but also painful moments of teaching Social Studies is addressing students' apathy and lack of concern about social issues. Initially, learners perceive the subject as a collection of dates and people to be remembered. It takes creativity and consistency to let them see the importance of social studies in their daily lives. Discussion of controversial issues, such as poverty and the environment, is painful since they need to consider different people in all walks of life.

Challenges in keeping the subject relevant are inevitable. Social Studies has strong connections with present social and political affairs, and as teachers, we need to update ourselves so that we can deliver factual information. The heavy load in lesson planning, implementation, and community involvement can at times be overwhelming, but these are responsibilities of every teacher in preparing students to become responsible citizens.

In indigenous communities, such as in Ifugao and Cordilleras, a Social Studies teacher's duty goes beyond educating students to preserving and promoting the cultural heritage of our people. In fact, with the rapid changes brought by modernization and globalization affecting younger Ifugaos, the role of Social Studies teachers in nurturing love for the culture, language, and traditions will be greater.

However, the pains of being a Social Studies teacher fade with every rewarding moment when students realize the importance of the subject to their own lives. Seeing students apply what they learned in their own lives provides teachers with immense gratification. The intellectual stimulation derived from the preparations is truly rewarding. Students' progress in critical thinking, discussion, participation, and realization of their role in society is what really motivates a teacher and makes him/her continue with the challenging profession.

One of the most satisfying gains of being a Social Studies teacher is helping students realize the importance of their identity and belonging to their community. In Ifugao, learning about the unique geography, their cultural significance, and other practices and beliefs, fosters pride in learners about the past of their ancestors and the need to preserve it. Every moment when a student feels a sense of belonging and commitment to their community, a teacher's

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mission to inculcate appreciation for their own identity and culture among them is being achieved.

The pains and gains of teaching Social Studies cannot be separated; the pains tested the teacher's dedication while the gains confirmed the teacher's noble purpose in developing informed citizens. Considering the dynamic, complex, socio-cultural, and environmental challenges today, Social Studies teachers' role in producing responsible and well-informed citizens is invaluable. Thus, the challenges, though many, can always be overcome with enthusiasm and with faith that one's purpose will never be wasted.